

Integrating 3GPP and Non-3GPP Technologies for Hybrid Positioning in B5G Networks

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Abstract— Positioning is crucial for Beyond 5G (B5G) networks, enabling applications like industrial automation, autonomous transportation, and augmented reality. Despite 3GPP's progress, seamless integration with non-3GPP technologies for indoor localization remains challenging. This work introduces a hybrid fingerprinting method that combines signal strength from both 3GPP and non-3GPP networks, utilizing a private 5G testbed with integrated Wi-Fi access points. The positioning algorithm operates as an xApp within the near-RT RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). We also propose a novel scheme to link non-3GPP networks with the RIC, enhancing real-time decision-making and improving localization accuracy. Experimental results confirm the effectiveness of our approach.

Keywords—B5G, Positioning, 3GPP, NON-3GPP, O-RAN, RIC, RAT, N3IWF

I. INTRODUCTION

Positioning is a critical aspect of future communication networks, enabling a wide range of applications that require precise localization, such as industrial automation, autonomous transportation, augmented and virtual reality, and logistics. As networks evolve beyond 5G (B5G) and towards 6G, positioning capabilities are expected to achieve centimeter-level accuracy, supporting real-time and mission-critical services in highly dynamic environments.

To meet these demands, the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has progressively enhanced positioning capabilities in its recent releases [1] [2]. Release 16 (Rel-16) introduced foundational techniques for positioning, including new reference signals, measurement enhancements, and architectural support to achieve improved accuracy. These advancements aimed at meeting the stringent requirements of applications such as industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), transportation, and logistics, where positioning accuracy of less than 3 meters and latency below 1 second are crucial. Release 17 (Rel-17) further refined these techniques, targeting centimeter-level precision and lower latency, making positioning more robust and efficient for time-sensitive applications. Looking ahead, Release 18 (Rel-18) is set to introduce additional enhancements, incorporating AI-driven localization techniques, improved signal processing methods, and better integration with non-terrestrial networks

A key component in this direction is the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which is responsible for all Radio Access Network (RAN) operation and optimization procedures [3]. It comprises the near-Real Time (near-RT) RIC [4] and the non-Real Time (non-RT) [5] RIC. The near-RT RIC handles real-time operations like network state information collection,

policy enforcement, and radio resource management optimization, while the non-RT RIC focuses on longer-term, non-time-sensitive functions. Positioning is facilitated through network-based measurements that are exposed to the near-RT RIC via the E2 interface. This interface uses a publish-subscribe mechanism to enable data exchange between External Applications (xApps) and RAN functions. The xApps can subscribe to one or more of these measurements and deploy Artificial Intelligence /Machine Learning (AI/ML) algorithms to accurately calculate or predict the position of the connected User Equipments (UEs)[6]. The E2 Application Protocol (E2AP) [8] defines signaling procedures for services like setup, reporting, and control, while E2 Service Models (E2SMs) enable specific interactions between xApps and RAN components, supporting applications such as Key Performance Metrics (KPM), Network Interfaces (NI), and RAN Control (RC).

As 5G is more and more adopted by private organizations and used in indoor environments, accurate indoor positioning is becoming increasingly crucial and challenging. Unlike outdoor positioning, which benefits from satellite-based technologies such as GPS, indoor positioning presents significant challenges due to signal attenuation, multipath effects, and the lack of direct line-of-sight with positioning satellites [9]. To address these challenges, 5G networks must integrate multiple positioning sources, combining 5G New Radio (5G NR)-based techniques with non-3GPP positioning technologies. 5G-NR can operate alongside Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, or satellite communications to create a seamless and heterogeneous connectivity ecosystem [10][11]. Non-3GPP devices can connect to 5G networks through mechanisms such as the Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF) [12]. This function ensures seamless integration of untrusted non-3GPP access technologies, enabling secure authentication, encryption, and data tunneling. Additionally, key 5G Core (5GC) components, such as the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) and the User Plane Function (UPF), play vital roles in managing connectivity and mobility across different radio access technologies (RATs).

One widely adopted technique for indoor positioning is fingerprinting [13], which relies on mapping signal characteristics, such as Received Signal Strength (RSS) or Channel State Information (CSI), to specific locations within an environment. Unlike model-based approaches that require precise knowledge of radio propagation conditions, fingerprinting leverages pre-collected signal measurements

to create a database of reference points. During real-time positioning, the device’s observed signals are compared to this database to estimate its location. This method is particularly effective in complex indoor spaces where multipath effects and signal attenuation make traditional ranging techniques unreliable. By combining 3GPP with non-3GPP measurements in a fingerprinting-based approach, positioning accuracy can be further enhanced, making it a key enabler for indoor localization in B5G networks.

However, a fundamental issue arises regarding how non-3GPP technologies can efficiently provide their positioning metrics to the 5G network in a way that enables real-time decision-making. Due to this, current positioning methods, remain largely fragmented, with 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies operating independently rather than in a unified framework. In this paper, we propose a novel approach that utilizes both technologies to enhance localization accuracy. Our setup collects signal strength measurements from a real 5G deployment while simultaneously gathering signal strength measurements from a Wi-Fi Access Point (AP). By leveraging these measurements, we demonstrate how the combination of 3GPP and non-3GPP signals can be used to accurately determine the UE’s location, using the fingerprint positioning method. Overall, the main contributions:

- We propose a hybrid fingerprint method that combines signal measurements retrieved from both 5G and WiFi Access Networks (ANs).
- The WiFi AP is part of the 5G network as a non-3GPP technology.
- The positioning is performed using real measurements that are extracted for both access technologies from a private 5G lab test-bed.
- The positioning algorithm is located/executed in the form of an xApp at a near-RT-RIC.
- We propose a novel architectural scheme for interconnecting non-3GPP access networks with the RIC.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents a literature review of the existing positioning methods in B5G systems. Section III provides a brief overview of the 5G architecture, followed by a detailed description of the system model. Section IV discusses the lab testbed and the implementation of the positioning scheme, along with the results and evaluations. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by highlighting the contributions and outlining future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Indoor positioning and localization techniques for 5G and beyond systems has attracted a lot of attention in the past few years. Designing efficient positioning system can be quite challenging due to that they are susceptible to phenomena such as multipath fading and shadowing. For this reason, most of the relevant works adopt fingerprint-based techniques that do not consider mathematical models and, hence, are less prone to errors compared to range-based schemes.

Authors in [14] propose an indoor positioning algorithm called 5G1M based on a Siamese network model. They use a

transfer learning method to handle long-term environmental changes and a trajectory-fitting method for the elimination of fluctuations in signal strengths. Their implementation is based on a 5G module and two outdoor base stations. Although their algorithm manages to improve the location accuracy compared to similar positioning approaches, they do not adopt the O-RAN paradigm [15] in their architecture nor the feature of multi-RAT connectivity through non-3GPP Access Networks.

A fingerprint-based indoor positioning system based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is proposed in [16] that adopts a transfer learning method that exploits CSI. For their experiments they use a combination of synthetic and real data extracted from a setup with a 5G module and six Access Points. Their results indicate an increase in the Average Improvement Ratio (AIR).

In [17] the authors propose an indoor positioning framework which uses a Bag-of-Features (BoF) model to transform raw RSS of the APs into robust and distinctive features in order to reduce the localization error. The proposed model is experimentally validated both by simulation-based indoor environments and real-time environments. Their results indicate improvement compared to similar works.

A control platform for fingerprint-based indoor localization in 4G/5G environments is presented in [19]. The authors propose a centralized Software Defined Radio (SDR) platform that controls indoor femto-cells to provide network-wide optimizations and operations. Their platform is built on top of OpenAirInterface (OAI) and is able to build, control and monitor radio-map of indoor environments for localization purposes. Their approach is experimentally tested, showing that their framework can improve the positioning results if the fingerprint maps are frequently updated.

Finally, the authors in [20] provide implementation details and tools that are required to perform UE positioning in 5G systems based on OAI. They also present an example use case based on Round-Trip Time (RTT) estimation, which is conducted on an OAI-based test-bed.

While these works have significantly advanced indoor positioning, several key gaps remain unaddressed. First, most of the aforementioned solutions either rely solely on 3GPP technologies or use non-3GPP signals independently, without fully exploiting the potential of multi-RAT integration. Additionally, the architectural integration with O-RAN and near-RT RIC components is often overlooked, limiting the practical deployment of intelligent and scalable positioning services. Inspired by the strengths of fingerprint-based techniques and recent efforts using deep learning and CSI features, our approach aims to unify 3GPP and non-3GPP signal sources—specifically 5G and Wi-Fi—within a cohesive RAN architecture. Unlike previous work, our solution leverages real-world signal measurements and is implemented as an xApp in a near-RT RIC, enabling efficient, real-time localization with cross-domain awareness.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

A. 5G Network Architecture

Figure 1 illustrates the 5G architecture, highlighting key components and interfaces that facilitate interconnectivity

Figure 1: Overall 5G Network architecture, adopting the O-RAN concept with support for non-3GPP access

within the 5G system. The O-RAN framework disaggregates traditional RAN functions, introducing software-defined intelligence and advanced control mechanisms. At the radio level, the Radio Unit (RU) handles transmission and reception of radio signals, interfacing with the Distributed Unit (DU) via the fronthaul (FH) link. The DU is responsible for real-time baseband processing and connects to the Centralized Unit (CU) over the F1 interface, which is divided into a control plane (F1-C) managing signaling and mobility control and a user plane (F1-U) handling user data transmission. The CU itself is split into the CU-Control Plane (CU-CP), responsible for network signaling and mobility procedures, and the CU-User Plane (CU-UP), which manages user data traffic.

To introduce network intelligence, the O-RAN architecture incorporates two key controllers: the near-RT RIC, which operates on timescales of milliseconds to seconds and optimizes RAN behavior via the E2 interface, and the Non-RT RIC, which provides long-term policy control, resource optimization, and analytics. The E2 interface establishes a connection between the near-RT RIC and E2 nodes, such as DUs, CUs, and O-RAN-compliant eNBs, utilizing a publish-subscribe mechanism to facilitate data exchange between xApps and RAN functions. Communication between the non-RT and near-RT RIC is facilitated by the A1 interface. The non-RT RIC is part of the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, which coordinates RAN resources through the O1 interface, ensuring efficient configuration and performance management. The two RICs open the road for the integration of AI and ML techniques in RAN, with AI models being trained in the non-RT RIC and then executed in the near-RT RIC to dynamically adjust network behavior.

Beyond the RAN, the 5G Core (5GC) serves as the backbone for multi-access integration, supporting both 3GPP and non-3GPP connectivity. The AMF handles user authentication, registration, and mobility management, while the Session Management Function (SMF) is responsible for session establishment and Quality of Service (QoS) enforcement. Other functions exist to support subscriber information storage, policy control, decision-making,

optimization, and predictive analytics as well as secure connection between external applications and the 5GC. Finally, the UPF routes user data traffic, ensuring low-latency communication between the network and external services over the N6 interface.

To support multi-access connectivity, the architecture integrates non-3GPP technologies such as Wi-Fi and satellite networks through the 5GC N3IWF. This function ensures seamless authentication, encryption, and tunneling between non-3GPP devices and the 5GC. Connectivity is established through the Nwu interface, which links non-3GPP devices to the network, while the N2 interface handles control signaling between the N3IWF and the 5GC, and the N3 interface facilitates user plane data exchange between non-3GPP networks and the 5GC.

The data flow in this architecture ensures seamless connectivity. UEs can access the network either through O-RAN or non-3GPP technologies, with traffic processed at the RAN level before being forwarded to the 5GC over the N2 (control plane) and N3 (user plane) interfaces. For non-3GPP access, the N3IWF enables secure interworking, ensuring a unified connection with the 5GC. The UPF then routes user data between the network and external applications over N6, supporting low-latency applications and location-based services.

B. Problem Formulation

We consider a multi-RAT environment that integrates both 5G-RAN and non-3GPP connectivity, as illustrated in Figure 1. The setup consists of a single 5G gNB and a Wi-Fi AP, enabling multi-RAT positioning. The UE is equipped with both 5G and Wi-Fi modules, allowing it to collect signal measurements from both technologies. The set of access nodes is defined as $B = \{b_{5G}, b_{WiFi}\}$ where b_{5G} represents the gNB and b_{WiFi} the WiFi AP. To obtain real-time signal data, the near-RT RIC collects signal strength indicators (e.g., RSSI, RSRP) from both the 5G and Wi-Fi networks via the E2 interface. These measurements are exposed to an xApp through standardized APIs. The xApp periodically queries the near-RT RIC to retrieve the latest measurements, which are then used to perform fingerprint-based positioning.

Fingerprint positioning is based on collecting signal characteristics at different locations and then match them with real-time data in order to estimate the location of the device. This is executed in a two-step process: an offline phase which includes the creation of fingerprint database, and an online phase where the real-time positioning takes place. During the offline phase, a predefined physical location (where the positioning will take place) is depicted as a grid with multiple reference points (RPs) where each RP acts as a ground truth location in order to train the system. The set of Reference Points is denoted as $RP = \{rp_1, rp_2, \dots\}$ with each reference point rp_i having known coordinates (x_i, y_i) . At every reference point rp_i the xApp collects Signal Measurements (SM) from both the 5G gNB and the Wi-Fi AP at fixed time intervals. Then, the SMs along with the corresponding reference point rp_i form a record $F_{p,i} = \{p_i, SM_{gNB}, SM_{WiFi}\}$ that is stored in a fingerprint database (radio-map).

The online phase follows once the fingerprint database is ready, where based on actual real-time SMs generated from the UE, the estimation of its location takes place. The UE

Table 1: Comparison of Approaches for Non-3GPP Positioning Data Integration

Approach	Description	Pros	Cons
UE-based Reporting	UE sends non-3GPP data (e.g., Wi-Fi positioning) directly to near-RT RIC via E2.	No added network elements; Simple architecture.	High UE dependency; Increased signaling load
E2 Agent in Non-3GPP Node	E2 agent embedded in Wi-Fi/AP node sends data to RIC.	Offloads UE; Network-controlled reporting.	New element required; High integration complexity.
N3IWF Extension	Extend N3IWF with E2 support to relay positioning data.	Leverages existing infra; Protocol alignment; Scalable.	Moderate changes to N3IWF; Standardization effort.

captures its signal parameters (5G/WiFi) in a location that it is unaware of, and sends them to the location where the positioning algorithm is executed (fingerprint database). These metrics are then compared with the radio-map measurements and finally the system makes an estimation for the position of the device based on the closest fingerprint match. If multiple locations are similar, weighted averaging or interpolation is used to refine accuracy.

C. Data Acquisition

A key challenge is determining how the necessary positioning metrics from non-3GPP access networks can be collected and provided to the 5G network in a way that allows the near-RT RIC to leverage these effectively. The xApp responsible for real-time positioning that is hosted in near-RT RIC requires continuous updates regarding user location from both 5G and non-3GPP networks. The primary issue that arises is how non-3GPP access networks can report their metrics through the 5G system in a standardized and efficient manner.

Three potential approaches can be considered for collecting and transmitting non-3GPP positioning data to the RIC. The first approach involves direct reporting from the UE through the E2 interface. In this case, the UE would be responsible for gathering Wi-Fi-based positioning data and transmitting it directly to the RIC. While this method eliminates the need for additional network elements, it places a higher dependency on the UE's capabilities and may lead to increased signaling overhead.

A second approach is to introduce a dedicated control element within the non-3GPP access node, embedding an E2 agent that communicates directly with the RIC. This would allow the Wi-Fi or other non-3GPP access points to handle positioning information independently of the UE and transmit the necessary data to the xApp. However, this approach requires the development of a new network element, along with the implementation of all the necessary background protocols, making it a more complex and resource-intensive solution.

A third approach, which presents a more practical and scalable solution, is to extend the functionality of the N3IWF to support the E2 agent. Since the N3IWF already serves as the main interworking point between non-3GPP networks and the 5GC, enhancing it with E2 support would allow it to act as a bridge between non-3GPP positioning sources and

the RIC. This approach benefits from the alignment of the transport protocols between the N3IWF and the E2 interface, simplifying the integration process. The N3IWF control plane protocol stack includes Next Generation Access Stratum (NGAS) Application Protocol (NGAP)[21] over SCTP [22], operating above IP and Ethernet or Wi-Fi at the lower layers. Similarly, the E2 interface, which facilitates communication between the near-RT RIC and RAN nodes also employs SCTP over IP, with E2AP handling control signaling at the application layer. This structural alignment suggests that the N3IWF could be extended to support E2-based interactions, enabling non-3GPP positioning data to be exposed to the near-RT RIC for further processing and optimization. Additionally, to minimize latency, the N3IWF could be co-located with the near-RT RIC, ensuring faster transmission of positioning data.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

A. Platform Description

The platform comprises several components that involve a stand-alone 5G network with multi-RAT connectivity support and a near-RT-RIC which provides near real time control and optimization. For the RAN segment we have used a containerized version of OpenAirInterface (OAI) that supports BaseBand functional split and is deployed in three distinct components, namely the Remote Unit (RU), the Distributed Unit (DU) and the Centralised Unit (CU). The 5GCN is based on a Virtual Machine (VM)-based free5GC [23] implementation where the CN Network Functions (NFs) are hosted in a central private cloud infrastructure. Additionally, our setup exploits the N3IWF functionality of the 5GC to provide multi-RAT connectivity through an untrusted WiFi AP. Finally, in this implementation we used EdgeRIC [24] as the near-RT-RIC. The gNB node is interconnected to edge RIC through E2 interfaces. The xApps can connect to near RT RIC and subscribe to UE performance metrics, e.g. Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) or Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), to perform positioning calculations.

B. Implementation

For the execution of the fingerprint positioning algorithm, we begin by dividing a predefined space into multiple grid points (as shown in Figure 2). This space covers 4 meters in

Figure 2: Experimental Area for Positioning. The area was divided into a 4x3 grid, with each block measuring 1m x 1m. The 5G gNB and the Wi-Fi AP were placed opposite each other.

length and 3 meters in width, and it is divided into 12 RPs, with equal distances between them. In our setup, the Wi-Fi AP (Teltonika RUTX50) and the gNB (OAI) are positioned at opposite ends of the grid. The UE used in this experiment was a Quectel device along with a Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) UE that connects to the Non-3GPP network.

To build the radio-map (or offline database), we collect multiple signal measurements from each RP, from both the Wi-Fi and 5G networks. Specifically, the 5G signal metrics captured by the Quectel UE are forwarded to the RIC via the E2 interface. For the Wi-Fi part, the COTS UE, collocated with the Quectel device (since the Quectel lacks a Wi-Fi NIC card), is used. The AP records the received signal strength from the connected device, and these metrics are exposed to the RIC. This procedure can be carried out using one of the three approaches discussed in Section III C.

After receiving the signal measurements from ANs, the RIC stores them in an in-memory database [25] creating a radio-map with multi-technology RAN measurements. The radio-map is then used to train a Support Vector Machines (SVM) classification ML model. The training ML models is ported in an xApp that uses as input real time RF measurements which are then mapped into position IDs. Figure 3 illustrates the actual trajectory of a UE alongside the trajectory estimated by the xApp. The xApp running the SVM model successfully tracks the UE's position across different RPs, achieving a high degree of accuracy in this controlled environment. The close alignment between the blue (actual) and red (estimated) lines indicates that the hybrid fingerprinting method effectively leverages both 5G and Wi-Fi signal metrics and mitigates the limitations of individual

Figure 3: Actual and xApp based estimated trajectories for a UE

technologies—such as 5G's susceptibility to shadowing and Wi-Fi's limited coverage—to significantly improve localization robustness, which is critical for real-time applications in dynamic indoor environments. Although the current setup is of small scale it provides an essential proof-of-concept validating the feasibility of integrating multi-RAT signal measurements into a unified positioning framework at the RIC level.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a hybrid fingerprinting-based approach that integrates 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to achieve enhanced localization accuracy. Through the implementation of a small-scale indoor testbed, we collected real-time signal measurements from both 5G and Wi-Fi networks, integrated them into a unified localization system via the near-RT RIC, and used an SVM model within an xApp for positioning. Our results show that leveraging both 5G and Wi-Fi mitigates the limitations of each technology, leading to a more accurate and robust positioning system. This work contributes a proof-of-concept for real-time hybrid localization in an O-RAN framework and presents a novel architecture for integrating non-3GPP data into the 5G control loop. The success of this implementation underscores the potential of incorporating non-3GPP technologies in future B5G and 6G networks to enhance network performance. Future work will focus on scaling the approach to larger environments, testing additional non-3GPP technologies, and advancing machine learning models to further improve positioning accuracy.

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